

PROTOTYPE OF NEW PROCESSED, NUTRIENT, AND NUTRACEUTICAL RICH FOOD RAW MATERIALS / INGREDIENTS

D5.11

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Short Description
<p>This documentation forms the basis for the realization of the project prototypes of new food raw materials and ingredients. Together with the prototype objectives, general considerations and recommendations, it provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototypes as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the in-field validation (WP5). According to the impact pathway approach, it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the obtained measures of main key performance indicators demonstrating the impact. The detailed functional and nutritional properties of the validated prototypes are reported in D5.16</p>

Dissemination level	
DEM	Prototype

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Abbreviations and glossary

Abbreviation/specialist term	Explanation
AAS	Atomic absorption spectroscopy
AOAC	Association of Official Analytical Chemists
AOAC	Association of Official Agricultural Chemists
BBR	Brightest Brilliant Red
KE	Kenya
KPI	Key performance indicator
MUAC	Mid Upper Arm Circumference
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OAI	Oil absorption index
OFSP	Orange fleshed sweet potatoes
SME	Small and medium enterprise
TN	Tunisia
TZ	Tanzania
UG	Uganda
WAI	Water Absorption Index
WSI	Water solubility index

1. General introduction

Limited dietary diversity is a contributing factor to malnutrition. FoodLAND sought to support nutrition performance improvement in selected food hubs by promoting agricultural biodiversity and food diversity. Identification of nutrient and nutraceutical rich ingredients and evaluating their performance in food products was adopted as one of the strategies towards improving nutrition. Hence a number of novel raw materials and ingredients were identified/ or produced through technological research. These are listed in Table 1 below.

Table 1: List of novel raw materials and ingredients from FoodLAND technological research

Food Hub	New food raw material / ingredient / food product
Mvomero/Morogoro (TZ)	Improved legume lines (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L.)
Kondar/Chebika (TN)	Composite wheat; legumes (pea, faba bean, chickpea) flour
Kondar/Chebika (TN)	Vegetables composite flours (leaf: parsley, spinach, chard; bulb: potato, carrot; spice: tomato, onion)
Kilombero (TZ)	Composite flour (white maize, millet, bio-fortified common beans, soybeans, and sesame seeds)
Kamuli (UG)	Orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, and bio-fortified beans flour
Laelay Machew (ET)	Composite moringa and teff flour
Mukurweiri, Kangundo (KE)	Therapeutic powder for diabetic people (tree tomato)
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Dried, salted, smoked, fermented fish (<i>Barbus altianalis</i> / <i>Labeo victorianus</i>)
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Dried fish (mullet, tilapia and eel, bottarga)
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Fish powder
Jendouba (TN)	Dried strawberries, dried eggplant, dried onions, dried tomatoes, dried pepper, dried salted dam fish fillets, bottarga
Kitui	Quinoa-maize composite flour

This deliverable reports about the above listed raw materials/ ingredients, briefly outlining their development, properties and utilization options. Details of the novel raw materials/ingredients development and characterization are contained in other deliverables. Primary processing techniques used in their production are reported in D5.10, while details of their nutrient and nutraceutical value as well as their functionality in food systems, are reported in D5.16. Due to their high nutrients and nutraceuticals content, the identified raw materials, ingredients and food products have potential to contribute to filling nutritional gaps identified in D2.5 and to realization of nutritional recommendations reported in D2.6.

Descriptions for individual prototypes follows, with activities, outputs, outcomes and anticipated impact included, based on the impact pathway approach (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Impact pathway

2. Descriptions for different raw materials and ingredients

2.1 New improved beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) lines

2.1.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is a vital legume crop, widely valued for its rich nutritional profile, making it an important staple food in many parts of the world (Hummel et al., 2018). The consumption of common bean in developing

countries is reported to be higher compared to developed countries due to its ready availability to most people in comparison to meats and fish which are relatively costly to the majority (Beebe et al., 2020; Broughton et al., 2003). In sub-Saharan Africa, common bean meets more than 50% of the dietary protein requirements; while in East Africa, it is a major staple, the second source of dietary protein, and the third most important source of calories after maize and cassava (Amongi et al., 2018; Broughton et al., 2003; Hillocks et al., 2006). Common bean is a valuable source of protein, vitamins, and minerals such as calcium, potassium, phosphorus, iron, copper, zinc, and magnesium. Zinc and iron are crucial to human well-being and an adequate supply of these nutrients helps to prevent iron deficiency anaemia and zinc deficiency (termed as “hidden hunger”), which are the two prevalent health concerns of the developing world (Blair et al., 2009).

Dietary sources of Fe and Zn could be from both animal and plants foods; however, the animal-based sources are not being consumed regularly in most poor households because they are relatively expensive compared to plant sources. This dictates that an adequate intake of Fe and Zn must come from plant-based foods and common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L) is one of the good and affordable sources of Fe and Zn.

Therefore, the main objective of this work is to use the selected new bean lines that combine high zinc & iron concentration as raw materials for production of composite flours.

2.1.2. Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for developing and utilising the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Cultivation of new lines of bean	M
2	Dryer for drying of beans	M
3	Hammer mills for milling of beans	M
4	Packaging materials (hermetic seal packaging)	M

* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low

2.1.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Production of beans flour

Bean seeds were sun-dried for a full day to ensure reduction of moisture content, thoroughly cleaned to remove any sand, stones, and other foreign materials. The cleaned beans were then milled using a hammer mill. After milling, the beans were ground into fine flour. The resulting flour was carefully packed into dry, clean, and sealed containers to prevent contamination and moisture absorption. The sealed containers were stored at room temperature, ensuring the flour remained dry and preserved to be used as an ingredient in the production of composite flour.

Laboratory analysis for proximate composition and physicochemical parameters of beans

Proximate analysis to determine the composition of the new bean lines, which formed the basis for mixing with other ingredients for the production of composite flour. In addition to the proximate analysis, the following physicochemical parameters were also evaluated: Water Absorption Index (WAI), Water Solubility Index (WSI), Oil Absorption Index (OAI), Bulk Density, and Angle of Repose. The detailed methods adopted for each parameter have been reported in D5.16.

Laboratory analysis for Fe and Zn in new bean lines

The micronutrients content (iron and zinc) of new bean lines was also determined using the atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) method (AOAC, 1995). The detailed procedures have been described in D5.16.

2.1.4 Summary of the outputs

2.1.3.1 Results and achievements

Proximate analysis of new lines of beans

The results demonstrate that the new line of beans possesses a well-balanced nutritional profile, featuring high protein content, moderate fat, and fiber levels. These findings suggest that the new line beans are an excellent ingredient for nutritional enhancement, particularly in the development of composite flours.

Only one new bean lines, NUA-629, was selected for use in composite flour due to its comparable high iron and zinc content. The detailed results are presented in Table 2.1.1. The moisture content of the new line beans was measured at 8.99%, which falls within the typical range for beans, indicating proper drying. This is important for ensuring the beans' shelf life and storage stability. The crude protein content was 18.03%, reflecting a high protein level, making these beans a valuable addition to composite flour formulations.

Furthermore, the crude fiber content was found to be 5.59%, contributing significantly to dietary fiber intake, which is essential for supporting digestive health. The crude fat content was 6.40%, which is moderate and contributes to the energy value of the beans. Lastly, the ash content was 3.26%, indicating a good mineral profile, which is vital for various physiological functions.

Table 2.1.1. Proximate analysis of new line of bean (NUA-629)

S/N	Parameter (%)	Mean \pm SD
1	Moisture content	8.99 \pm 0.69
2	Crude protein	18.03 \pm 0.91
3	Crude fiber	5.59 \pm 0.19
4	Crude fat	6.40 \pm 0.49
5	Ash content	3.26 \pm 0.35

Physicochemical properties of new lines of bean

The physicochemical properties of the new line of bean flour were analyzed to evaluate its suitability for use in composite flour. These properties are essential for determining the behavior of the flour during processing and its final product quality. The parameters measured included the Water Absorption Index (WAI), Water Solubility Index (WSI), Oil Absorption Index (OAI), Bulk Density, and Angle of Repose. The results of these analyses are presented below. Table 2.1.2 presents the report for a single new variety of bean, NUA-629.

Table 2.1.2. Physico-chemical properties of new line of bean (NUA-629)

S/N	Parameters	Mean \pm SD
1	Water absorption index (WAI) (%)	4.87 \pm 0.07
2	Water solubility index (WSI) (%)	42.5 \pm 1.32
3	Oil absorption index (OAI) (mL/100g)	1.24 \pm 0.15
4	Bulk density, (g/cm ³)	0.57 \pm 0.01
5	Angle of Repose (°)	71.45 \pm 0.39

Water Absorption Index (WAI): The WAI of 4.87% indicates that the biofortified flour has a moderate ability to absorb water. This property is important for its behavior in dough formation and hydration during processing.

Water Solubility Index (WSI): With a WSI of 42.5%, the new lines bean flour demonstrates a moderate level of solubility in water. This indicates that the flour will disperse easily in water, which may be useful for applications requiring dissolution, such as composite flour. In addition, **oil Absorption Index (OAI):** The OAI value of 1.24 mL/100g suggests that the beans flour has a relatively low oil absorption capacity. This is important for the texture and consistency of the products in which the flour is used, as it may influence the fat content of the final product.

Bulk Density: The bulk density of 0.57 g/cm³ indicates that the flour is light and porous, which is typical for flour with good flow properties. This property influences the ease of handling, storage, and packaging of the flour.

Angle of Repose: The angle of repose of 71.45° suggests that the biofortified flour has a moderate flowability. The angle of repose is a key factor in determining the handling properties of flour during processing, such as in conveyors and hoppers.

Iron and zinc contents of new line of beans

This results of the iron and zinc content data of new bean lines are shown in Table 2.1.3 and the selected beans lines are shown in Figure 2.1.1.

Table 2.1.3. Zinc and iron content of selected beans lines

Bean lines	Zn content (mg/100 g)	Fe content (mg/100 g)
16TZMBYPIC-130-1	28.6	103.8
Lyamungo 90 (check)	28.7	119.7
Mashamba-PYT-4	26.8	125.6
NUA-590	26.4	98.6
NUA-629	29.7	131.3
NUA-660	25.9	99.8

Zinc content: The zinc content in the bean lines ranges from 25.9 mg/kg (NUA-660) to 29.7 mg/100 g (NUA-629). The highest concentration of zinc was found in the NUA-629 variety, while the lowest was observed in NUA-660. The check variety (control), Lyamungo 90, has a similar zinc content (28.7 mg/100 g) to several of the biofortified lines, suggesting that biofortification efforts have achieved comparable zinc levels. Moreover, iron content in the biofortified bean lines varies from 98.6 mg/100 g (NUA-590) to 131.3 mg/100 g (NUA-629). The NUA-629 bean line also exhibits the highest iron content among the varieties tested. The iron content in the check variety, Lyamungo 90, is 119.7 mg/100 g, which is higher than most of the biofortified lines except for Mashamba-PYT-4 and NUA-629. This suggests that biofortification efforts have successfully increased iron levels in certain lines, especially NUA-629.

Figure 2.1.1: Photo showing seeds of the selected bean lines; (a) NUA 660, (b) NUA 629, (c) Mashamba -PTY-4 and (d) 16TZMBYPIC-130-1.

2.1.4.2 Relevant production

Publications

Mvile, A. J, Nchimbi-Msolla S., Tryphone G. M. 2023. Elucidating the Effect of Genotype x Environment Interaction and Storage Time on Cooking Time of Selected Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Genotypes. East African Journal of Science, Technology and Innovations (EAJSTI) Vol. 4 (Special Issue2).

Conference paper

Mvile, A. J, Nchimbi-Msolla S., Tryphone G. M. 2024. Genotype x Environment interaction of selected Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Genotypes for Fe and Zn concentration. The 9th Science, Technology and Innovation for Sustainable Development Conference to be held in Dar es salaam Tanzania 11-13 September 2024 (*paper submitted for publication*).

2.1.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Mvomero (TZ)	improved bean lines	20 farmers and food processors

2.1.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Mvomera (TZ)	Improved legume lines (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L.)	Number of lines with increased mineral composition of Fe and Zn and improved yield

		<p>selected (at least 2 varieties selected with improved traits)</p> <p>Bean farmers using improved varieties (at least 50% bean farmers who were trained are trying new bean in their own farms)</p> <p>Increased yield performance of new bean lines (on average the new varieties are performing at least 15% higher compared to local varieties)</p> <p>Increase income of farmers by selling bean with attractive traits for market (Seed colour, good seed size and short cooking time selected (at least 20% increase)</p>
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

Over time, the improved beans lines are expected to lead to:

- Improved food security for households in Mvomero Food Hub and beyond
- Improved nutritional status of members in the households
- Increased income since beans are sold to traders for urban market

2.1.7 Conclusions

The new bean lines demonstrate significant improvements in both protein content and micronutrient levels, particularly in zinc and iron, making them an excellent ingredient for composite flour production. This is a promising approach to addressing micronutrient deficiencies in sub-Saharan Africa. With a high protein content (18.03%), moderate fat (6.40%), and substantial fiber (5.59%), these beans hold great potential for enhancing the nutritional value of composite flour formulations. Additionally, their favorable physicochemical properties, including water and oil absorption, bulk density, and flowability, indicate they will perform well in a variety of food applications. These biofortified beans offer the potential to improve food security and overall health in regions suffering

from micronutrient deficiencies, particularly among vulnerable groups such as children and pregnant women. Their promising nutritional profile and versatility suggest that these bean varieties will be widely adopted, not only within the Food Hub but also in broader markets.

2.2 Composite flour of wheat, faba bean and pea for soup “Hsou”

2.2.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Problem(s) the prototype aims to solve or the user needs intends to address, concept, specific objectives and targets (with special attention to gender issues).

Wheat is a staple food in Tunisia, playing a central role in the country's diet and food culture. As one of the primary ingredients in bread, pasta, couscous, and other traditional dishes, wheat consumption is deeply ingrained in Tunisian culinary practices. The average Tunisian diet relies heavily on wheat-based products, making the country one of the highest per capita consumers of wheat in the world. This high consumption is driven by the affordability and versatility of wheat products, which form a significant portion of daily caloric intake for many households. However, the reliance on wheat poses challenges, including vulnerability to fluctuations in global wheat prices and the need for imports to meet domestic demand, as local production is insufficient. Additionally, the nutritional limitations of a wheat-heavy diet highlight the importance of diversifying food sources to address potential micronutrient deficiencies and improve overall health outcomes. Therefore, the composite flour, combining wheat with legumes such as faba bean and pea the most cultivated legumes in the food hub Enfidha/Chebika, aims to address several critical challenges in food preparation and nutrition. This innovative product is designed to enhance dietary diversity, increase the nutritional value of soups, and provide a cost-effective alternative to traditional wheat flour. By integrating legumes, the flour targets a higher protein content, essential amino acids, and better fiber intake, catering to populations with limited access to high-protein foods. The prototype also considers specific user needs, including dietary preferences, affordability, and ease of use in soup preparation. Furthermore, the development process emphasizes gender inclusivity, recognizing the role of women as primary

caregivers and food preparers in many communities. Many non-governmental organizations are encouraging the women involvement in the food value chain. The objectives include improving household nutrition, reducing nutritional deficiency risks, and empowering women by offering a product that supports their role in family health management while promoting gender equity through targeted marketing and training programs.

2.2.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for development and implementation of the prototype are provided below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Dryer: to ensure the same water content of the different raw material	1
2	Milling machines: Required to grind wheat, faba beans, and peas into fine, uniform particles.	M
3	Blending equipment: Used to mix the flours in precise ratios to achieve desired functionality and consistency.	M
4	Sieving and particle size grading machines: Ensure uniformity in texture.	1
5	Packaging machines: For airtight and moisture-proof sealing to maintain product quality.	2
6	Storage facilities: Temperature- and humidity-controlled units to prevent spoilage.	1
7	Raw materials: Wheat grains: Base ingredient for the composite flour. Faba beans and peas: High-protein legumes for nutritional enhancement.	M
8	Production operators: To handle milling, blending, and packaging processes.	M
9	Quality assurance specialist: To test and ensure consistency in product standards	2
10	Costs: Raw material procurement: Major cost component based on quantity and quality of grains and legumes. Equipment acquisition or leasing: High initial cost for milling, blending, and packaging machineries. Facility setup and maintenance: Includes costs for space, utilities, and safety compliance. Labor costs: Salaries for personnel involved in production and quality assurance.	M

11	Production Facilities: A clean, food-safe environment with sufficient space for milling, blending, packaging.	M
12	Storage Units: Temperature- and humidity-controlled storage areas for raw materials (wheat, faba beans, peas) and finished products to prevent spoilage and maintain quality.	1
13	Utilities: Reliable electricity supply for operating equipment. Access to clean water for sanitation and maintenance.	M
14	Adequate ventilation systems for a safe working environment.	M
15	Transportation and Logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
16	Waste Management Systems: Facilities for handling and disposing of by-products or waste materials in an eco-friendly manner.	2
17	Safety and Compliance Infrastructure: Fire safety systems, first aid kits, and emergency exits for worker safety.	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.2.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The selection of ingredients (wheat and legumes) was based on survey results about the agricultural products diversity in the food hub Enfidha/Chebika. Selected legumes were faba bean, chickpea and pea, they were subjected to different pretreatment (microwave and germination) and tested for nutritional properties (water content, crude proteins, phenolic content, antioxidant activity) and functional properties (bulk density, tapped density, water and oil absorption capacities, swelling capacity...) and color parameters.

Composite flours Formulation: was based on mixing plane methodology generated by Expert Design 13 software that gives different formulations. Three substitution wheat flour levels were tested (10, 15 and 20%) using untreated, microwave heated and germinated legumes. Composite flours were subjected to the same analysis of raw material.

Based on the characterization results, one formulation of the composite flour of wheat and legumes was validated (Figure 2.2.1).

Figure 2.2.1. Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating of composite flour of wheat and legumes

2.2.4 Summary of the outputs

2.2.4.1 Results and achievements

The development of composite flour made from wheat and legume flours, (faba bean and pea), represents an innovative approach to enhancing nutritional value and sustainability in food production. This technology combines traditional wheat flour with legume-based alternatives to create a high-protein, fiber-rich product suitable for diverse applications in baking and cooking. Advanced milling and blending processes ensure uniform particle size and optimal functional properties, such as improved flour water absorption capacity. This composite flour leverages legumes' natural benefits, including their phenolic content and antioxidant activity, while promoting sustainable agriculture through the reduced reliance on solely wheat-based production. The result is a versatile, nutritious, and eco-friendly product catering to the demands of health-conscious and environmentally-aware consumers.

2.2.4.2 Relevant production

An article will be submitted in January 2025. Expected title: “Development and Optimization of Composite Flours from Wheat and Pretreated Legumes: A Functional, Nutritional, and Formulation-Based Study”

2.2.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Enfidha/Chebika	Milling (composite flour of wheat and legumes)	Farmers (4) SMEs (1) NGOs: GDA Kharroub Enfidha (12 operators) GDA Chebika (15 operators)

2.2.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Enfidha/Chebika	Milling (composite flour of wheat and legumes)	Technology : KPI definition: KPI1: partnership extension index (PEI) (measures partnership growth and success, collaboration between the different stakeholders in the value chain PEI = 6/10. The collaboration among the various stakeholders was satisfactory but requires further effort to ensure the sustainability of the

		<p>partnership. Governmental organizations play a vital role in strengthening relationships between stakeholders</p> <p>KPI2: sustainability score (SS) (measures the environmental and socio economic impacts)</p> <p>SS =7/10: this score is given since the ingredients are sourced sustainably and locally. Legumes are nitrogen-fixing plants, meaning they improve soil fertility and reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers, which lowers greenhouse gas emissions. They are a sustainable source of protein and help diversify crop rotations, contributing to improved soil health and reduced pest pressures.</p> <p>Substituting a portion of wheat with legume flours can reduce reliance on monoculture wheat farming, which has a higher environmental footprint.</p> <p>Nutritional:</p> <p>KPI definition: KPI1: Ingredient quality index (IQI) ((used to measure the global quality of ingredients included in the product)</p>
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		<p>-IQI=9/10: this score is based on quality analysis results, an improvement in nutritional properties was recorded with the maintaining of flour functional properties</p>
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.2.7 Conclusions

In conclusion, the successful implementation of composite flour production has significant potential for growth, both in terms of market acceptance and operational efficiency. However, continuous innovation and adaptation are crucial for maintaining competitiveness in the market. By focusing on process optimization, sustainability, and R&D, the business can position itself as a leader in the development of nutritious, sustainable food products.

Recommendations: Expand market reach, optimize production, and explore technological advancements. Implications: Organizational, operational, and policy adaptations will be necessary for scaling. Way Forward: Invest in research and partnerships to continue innovating and expanding.

2.3 Vegetables composite flour for soup (Broudou) preparation

2.3.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

The vegetable composite flour prototype aims to address key nutritional challenges faced by children and women in Tunisia, particularly in areas where access to a varied and nutritious diet is limited. By combining seven dried vegetables: parsley, chard, spinach, potato, carrot, tomato, and onion, this

product offers a nutrient-dense, convenient solution to enhance the nutritional quality of soups, a common meal in many households. The primary objectives of the prototype are to provide an affordable, accessible, and easy-to-prepare product that addresses micronutrient deficiencies, especially those related to vitamins and minerals critical for growth, immunity, and maternal health. The product specifically targets the nutritional needs of women and children, who are most vulnerable to malnutrition. By improving the nutritional profile of daily meals, this innovation seeks to support healthier diets, especially for women in reproductive age and children in their growth years. Gender issues are addressed by promoting food security for women, who often manage household nutrition, and by offering opportunity to create new jobs.

2.3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for development and implementation of the prototype are given below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Dryer: will be used for vegetable drying to ensure the same water content of the different raw material	M
2	Milling machines: Required to grind dried vegetables into fine, uniform particles.	M
3	Blending equipment: Used to mix the flours in precise ratios to achieve desired functionality and consistency.	1
4	Sieving and particle size grading machines: Ensure uniformity in texture.	1
5	Packaging machines: For airtight and moisture-proof sealing to maintain product quality.	2
6	Storage facilities: Temperature- and humidity-controlled units to prevent spoilage.	1
7	Raw materials: vegetables should be selected for their quality	M
8	Production operators: To handle milling, blending, and packaging processes.	M
9	Quality assurance specialist: To test and ensure consistency in product standards	2
10	Costs: Raw material procurement: Major cost component based on quantity and quality of vegetables.	M

	Equipment acquisition or leasing: High initial cost for milling, blending, and packaging machineries. Facility setup and maintenance: Includes costs for space, utilities, and safety compliance. Labor costs: Salaries for personnel involved in production and quality assurance.	
11	Production Facilities: A clean, food-safe environment with sufficient space for milling, blending, packaging.	M
12	Storage Units: Temperature- and humidity-controlled storage areas for raw materials (fresh vegetables) and finished products to prevent spoilage and maintain quality.	1
13	Utilities: Reliable electricity supply for operating equipment. Access to clean water for sanitation and maintenance.	M
14	Adequate ventilation systems for a safe working environment.	M
15	Transportation and Logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
16	Waste Management Systems: Facilities for handling and disposing of by-products or waste materials in an eco-friendly manner.	2
17	Safety and Compliance Infrastructure: Fire safety systems, first aid kits, and emergency exits for worker safety.	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.3.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Seven vegetables collected from Enfidha/Chebika food hub, dried and sieved at two particle sizes. Then, were characterized for their nutritional and functional properties. The formulation process was guided by an experimental mixture design, optimizing the ratios of the seven vegetables to achieve the desired nutritional profile and functional properties. One formulation with two particle sizes was tested for soup preparation and subjected to sensory evaluations with target users to determine palatability and satisfaction with flavor, texture, and appearance. For validation, selection criteria emphasized nutritional density, sensory acceptability, and ease of incorporation into culinary applications. The formulation with the smaller particle size was validated. The prototype underwent detailed physicochemical analyses to assess nutritional and functional properties (Figure 2.4.1).

Figure 2.3.1. Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating of prototype vegetables composite flour, PS: particle size

2.3.4 Summary of the outputs

2.3.4.1 Results and achievements

Short description of the new food raw materials / ingredients.

The development of the vegetable composite flour employed advanced formulation techniques, leveraging an experimental mixture design to optimize the nutritional and functional properties of seven dried vegetables: chard, parsley, spinach, tomato, potato, carrot, and onion. Results revealed that particle size significantly influenced both nutritional and functional characteristics. Specifically, leafy vegetables and tomatoes exhibited the highest phenol content and antioxidant activity, reflecting their potential health benefits. In contrast, bulbs like onion and potato demonstrated lower antioxidant activity but excelled in functional properties, making them highly suitable for soup preparation.

Further analysis highlighted that the nutritional and functional properties of the flour formulations varied significantly based on the proportions of leafy vegetables, bulbs, and spices. Sensory evaluations indicated that soups prepared with the finer particle size were more appreciated by tasters due to their smoother texture and enhanced flavor integration.

Validation tests confirmed the composite flour's nutritional integrity, demonstrating its ability to retain key micronutrients and functional attributes even after preparation. This innovative product stands out as a versatile and nutritious ingredient, addressing dietary needs.

2.3.4.2 Relevant production

- Graduate student project report entitled: “Study on the Feasibility of Implementing a - Graduate student project report entitled: “Study on the Feasibility of Implementing a Dried Vegetable-Based Soup Production Project”
- An article will be submitted in 2025. Expected title: “Development and Optimization of a Dried Vegetable composite flour-Based Soup: Nutritional, Functional, and Sensory Evaluation”

2.3.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Enfidha/Chebika	Vegetables composite flour for soup preparation	Farmers (5) SMEs (1) NGOs: GDA Kharroub Enfidha (12 operators) GDA Chebika (15 operators)

2.3.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Enfidha/Chebika	Milling (Vegetables composite flour)	Technology : KPI definition: KPI1: partnership extension index (measures partnership growth and success, collaboration)

		<p>between the different stakeholders in the value chain</p> <p>PEI = 6/10. The collaboration among the various stakeholders was satisfactory but requires further effort to ensure the sustainability of the partnership. Governmental organizations play a vital role in strengthening relationships between stakeholders</p> <p>KPI2: sustainability score(measures the environmental and socio economic impacts)</p> <p>-SS=8/10: The composite flour of dried vegetables scores high on sustainability due to its potential to reduce food waste, improve nutrition, and support local agriculture. However, the score is slightly reduced due to energy use concerns during drying and potential accessibility issues.</p> <p>Nutritional:</p> <p>KPI definition: KPI1: Ingredient quality index ((used to measure the global quality of ingredients included in the product)</p> <p>IQI=9/10: The product is based on seven vegetables (parsley, chard, spinach, potato, carrot, tomato, and onion), all rich in essential vitamins, minerals,</p>
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		<p>fiber, and antioxidants. The diversity of ingredients ensures a broad spectrum of nutrients, enhancing the overall nutritional profile.</p> <p>KPI2: customer satisfaction assessment (measures the level of consumer satisfaction).</p> <p>CSA=7/10: both particle sizes were accepted by consumers with scores of 5.45/6 and 4.85/6 for particle size $\varphi < 0.5\text{mm}$ and $\varphi > 0.5\text{mm}$ respectively</p>
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.3.7 Conclusions

The vegetable composite flour innovation holds significant promise for improving the nutritional well-being of children and women in Tunisia. This innovation, built on a foundation of locally sourced, nutrient-rich vegetables, offers a practical, affordable, and culturally appropriate solution to malnutrition. While the prototype has been successfully tested and validated, its scalability and long-term impact depend on careful planning and execution across multiple dimensions. By addressing challenges related to scaling, market adoption, and operational efficiency, this product can serve as a model for similar initiatives globally. The way forward lies in leveraging technology, fostering partnerships, and maintaining a strong focus on consumer needs to ensure lasting impact and sustainability.

2.4 Cereal-legume composite flour

2.4.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Composite flour made from a blend of white maize, millets, soybeans, biofortified common beans, and sesame aims to address the prevalent malnutrition and micronutrient deficiencies in children, particularly in Mvomero Food Hub Morogoro, Tanzania. Many children in Tanzania suffer from "hidden hunger," which refers to a lack of essential vitamins and minerals, such as iron and zinc, leading to stunted growth, cognitive impairments, and weakened immune systems. Zinc and iron minerals are crucial to human well-being and an adequate supply of these nutrients helps to prevent iron deficiency anaemia and zinc deficiency, which are prevalent health concerns of the developing world (Blair et al., 2010). According to the Tanzania Demographic and Health Survey and Malaria Survey Indicator Survey (TDHS-MIS, 2015-16), almost half (45%) of Tanzanian women of reproductive age (15-49 years) are anaemic; with 33% being mildly anaemic; 11% moderately anaemic and 1% severely anaemic. According to Cowling (2024) about 31.8% of children under five years suffered from chronic malnutrition in Tanzania. The primary objective of this composite flour is to provide a balanced, nutrient-dense alternative to traditional staple foods by combining high-protein, high-fiber, and micronutrient-rich ingredients like biofortified beans and sesame, which can significantly enhance children's nutritional intake. By fortifying this flour with essential micronutrients from biofortified common beans, the product aims to combat iron and zinc deficiencies that affect children's health and development. The specific targets of this prototype are to improve children's overall nutrition, reduce the prevalence of malnutrition, and enhance cognitive and physical development. A key focus is on gender equality, ensuring that both boys and girls in underserved areas have equal access to composite flours. Special attention is given to the people of the Mvomero Food Hub as per D 2.5. By promoting the use of locally grown, biofortified beans, white maize and sesame, this initiative also supports sustainable agriculture and local economies. Two types of composite flour were produced (i.e., extruded and non-extruded). The composite flour offers a practical, culturally acceptable, and affordable solution for enhancing childhood nutrition, addressing both immediate health needs and long-term developmental goals.

2.4.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for development and implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	White maize or maize flour	M
2	Biofortified (new line) of common beans	M
3	Millet	M
4	Soybeans	M
5	Sesame	M
6	Electric oven drier for drying ingredients	M
7	Hammer mills for milling ingredients	M
8	Extruder for extruded composite flour	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.4.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Selection of raw materials for composite flour

The first stage involved selecting local raw materials for the production of composite flours. The materials chosen were white maize, millet, soybeans, biofortified common beans, sesame seeds, and sugar, each selected for its specific nutritional benefits. Millet was chosen to enhance the fiber content of the flour, while soybeans were included to boost the protein content. Biofortified common beans were selected for their high iron and zinc content, and white maize was chosen for its contribution to the energy content.

Formulation of composite flour

Four formulations were selected for testing based on locally available food ingredients and the WHO/UNICEF guidelines for total energy and protein content. In this study the Nutrisurvey software (2007) was used to generate the corresponding proportions of white maize, millets, soybeans, biofortified beans and sesame seeds in composite flour formulations and nutrient optimization. The

nutrients optimised were protein, fat, fiber, zinc, iron, calcium, and vitamins A. The optimisation was done to ensure that each formulation provided more than 40% of the daily recommended intake in a single meal for children under two. The four blends were formulated in triplicates as shown in Table 2.4.1. Note: Three 3% sugar was included to enhance the flavor of the final products.

Table 2.4.1. Ingredients and formulation for composite flour

Formulation	White maize (%)	Millet (%)	Soybean (%)	Biofortified common beans (%)	Sesame seeds (%)	Sugar for taste (%)
1	60	10	10	15	5	3
2	50	15	10	20	5	3
3	52	10	10	25	3	3
4	53	5	7	30	5	3

Production of composite flour

For each formulation, two types of composite flour were produced: extruded and non-extruded. After cleaning and washing to remove extraneous matter, all ingredients were dried in a hot air dryer at 60°C for 5 hours. For the extruded composite flour, all ingredients except for the millets and sesame seeds were milled to obtain flour. The milled mixture was processed using a single twin-screw extruder (Kneader Model EX 80), manufactured by Chaoyuan Powder Machinery Co. Ltd (China). The operating conditions were set at a screw speed of 200-400 RPM, a feed rate of 10-15 kg/h, and a die diameter of 2-3 mm. The temperature profile in the barrel zone towards the die was maintained at 100-115°C. After extrusion, the product (extruded) Figure 2.4.1 was cooled at room temperature for one hour and then milled in a hammer mill. The milled product was sieved through a 0.6-1.0 mm sieve. For the non-extruded composite flour, the same process was followed, except the mixture was not passed through the extruder.

Figure 2.4.1. Extruded before milling

Testing of composite flour

To validate the composite flour produced (Figure 2.4.2), several tests were conducted, including proximate analysis, sensory evaluation, micronutrient and vitamin analysis, physicochemical property assessments, and a shelf-life study. For the proximate analysis, moisture content, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, and ash content were determined. In the sensory evaluation, porridge was prepared from each flour formulation and provided to mothers or caregivers for assessment. Formulations 1 and 3 were selected as the best in terms of sensory acceptability. For the micronutrient analysis, several minerals, including iron and zinc, were measured. In addition, physicochemical properties such as water absorption index, water solubility index, oil absorption index, bulk density, and angle of repose were evaluated. To assess the storability and shelf-life of both extruded and non-extruded flours, a shelf-life study was conducted.

Figure 2.4.2. Composite flour: right extruded (produced by SUA) and left non-extruded (produced by SMEs- KATUNDU)

2.2.1.5 Shelf-life study of composite flour

The shelf-life study of the composite flours was conducted over a period of five months, from December 2023 to July 2024. In brief, composite flour samples (approximately 250 g each) were packed in three types of packaging materials: PPnC (biodegradable) film with paper bags, paper bags, and polyethylene bags, each measuring approximately 20 x 20 cm. Paper bags and polyethylene bags served as control packaging materials. For samples packaged in PPnC film, the primary packaging consisted of the film itself, while the secondary packaging was made of paper. This dual-layer approach was used to provide enhanced protection against physical damage and ensure the product's safety.

The samples were stored under two different temperature conditions: room temperature ($25 \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) and refrigerated temperature ($4 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) throughout the study period. Relative humidity was monitored continuously during the experiment. The room temperature conditions maintained an average relative humidity of 65% (ranging from 60% to 70%), while the refrigerated environment had an average relative humidity of $85\% \pm 5\%$.

The experimental design followed a completely randomized design (CRD) with three factors, each replicated three times. The factors included: (i) storage temperature ($4 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $25 \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$); (ii) packaging materials (PPnC film + paper

bags, paper bags, and polyethylene bags). The sampling time were 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 105, 120, 135, and 150 days.

For each flour product, packaging condition, and storage condition, a total of 240 pouches were prepared (10 pouches per packaging type x 3 packaging types = 30 pouches x 2 storage conditions = 60 pouches x 2 flour types = 120 pouches x 2 repetitions = 240 pouches). Samples for each parameter were collected in duplicate every 15 days for evaluation of physicochemical properties and microbial quality. The analyzed parameters included moisture content, water activity, bulk density, color, and microbial counts (total bacteria, yeast, and mold). Figure 2.4.3 outlines the design of the shelf-life study.

Figure 2.4.3. Illustrates the layout of the shelf-life study experiment

2.4.4 Summary of the outputs

2.4.4.1 Results and achievements

To validate the composite flour produced several analysis were performed check for the nutritional contents, physical characteristics, and shelf life study.

Proximate analysis of composite flour

The results of proximate analysis of two composite flour produced are presented in Table 2.4.1. The parameter analysed include moisture content, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat and ash content.

Table 2.4.1. Proximate analysis results for composite flour

S/ N	Sample	Moisture content (%)	Crude protein (%)	Crude fiber (%)	Crude fat (%)	Ash content (%)
1	Non-extruded composite flour	3.99 ± 0.69 ^a	15.22 ± 1.01 ^a	3.36 ± 0.20 ^a	3.43 ± 0.06 ^b	2.39 ± 0.25 ^a
2	Extruded composite flour	3.07 ± 0.04 ^b	12.9 ± 0.71 ^b	0.46 ± 0.05 ^b	4.48 ± 0.32 ^a	2.22 ± 0.13 ^a

The moisture content of non-extruded composite flour ($3.99 \pm 0.69\%$) is higher than that of extruded flour ($3.07 \pm 0.04\%$), likely due to the high temperature and pressure involved in the extrusion process, which reduces moisture. For crude protein, the extruded flour contains lower levels compared to the non-extruded flour, possibly due to protein denaturation during extrusion. A significant difference in crude fiber was observed, with extruded flour having considerably less fiber, likely due to the breakdown of fiber structures under high heat and pressure. Additionally, extruded flour had a higher crude fat content ($4.48 \pm 0.32\%$) than non-extruded flour ($3.43 \pm 0.06\%$), which may be a result of fat retention or modification during thermal processing. The ash content in the extruded flour ($2.22 \pm 0.13\%$) was slightly lower than in the non-extruded flour ($2.39 \pm 0.25\%$). Overall, extrusion reduces protein and fiber while increasing fat content, while non-extruded flour retains more moisture and minerals. These changes suggest that extrusion significantly alters the nutritional profile of

composite flour, potentially influencing its functional properties and applications in food products.

Table 2.4.2. Physico-chemical properties of composite flour

S/ N	Sample	Water absorption index 'WAI'	Water solubility index 'WSI'	Oil absorption index 'OAI'	Bulk density, g/cm ³	Angle of Repose
1	Non-extruded composite flour	5.20 ± 0.15 ^b	16.5 ± 1.35 ^b	2.14 ± 0.10 ^a	0.66 ± 0.06 ^a	74.2 ± 1.49 ^a
	Extruded composite flour	7.41 ± 0.31 ^a	38.0 ± 3.53 ^a	1.36 ± 0.44 ^b	0.50 ± 0.04 ^a	65.75 ± 1.56 ^b

The physico-chemical properties of composite flour produced are shown in Table 2.4.2. The value of WAI was higher in the extruded flour (7.41 ± 0.31) compared to the non-extruded flour (5.20 ± 0.15), indicating that the extruded flour has a greater capacity to absorb water. Similarly, the WSI of the extruded flour (38.0 ± 3.53) was much higher than the non-extruded flour (16.5 ± 1.35), suggesting that extrusion increases the solubility of the flour in water. In contrast, the OAI was lower in the extruded flour (1.36 ± 0.44) compared to the non-extruded flour (2.14 ± 0.10), indicating that non-extruded flour has a greater ability to absorb oil. In addition, the result of the bulk density of the extruded flour (0.50 ± 0.04 g/cm³) is lower than the non-extruded flour (0.66 ± 0.06 g/cm³). Lastly, the angle of repose is lower for the extruded flour (65.75 ± 1.56°) than the non-extruded flour (74.2 ± 1.49°), indicating that the extruded flour flows more easily.

Table 2.4.3. Micronutrients and vitamin contents of composite flour

Minerals contents mg/kg, except K is in %										
Product	β caroteno ids μg/100 g	Total phenol mg/100 g	Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn	Ca	Mg	K %	Na

Non-extruded composite flour	77.87 ± 3.12 ^b	1.18 ± 0.12 ^a	4.31 ± 0.31 ^a	41.42 ± 0.38 ^a	165.9 ± 0.01 ^a	25.68 ± 0.23 ^a	13.06 ± 0.05 ^a	254.6 ± 3.05 ^a	0.33 ± 0.03 ^a	125.34 ± 1.25 ^a
Extruded composite flour	87.30 ± 1.30 ^a	1.31 ± 0.07 ^a	4.51 ± 0.14 ^a	42.59 ± 0.82 ^a	198.5 ± 1.81 ^a	27.29 ± 0.19 ^a	11.88 ± 0.77 ^a	302.2 ± 4.12 ^b	0.36 ± 0.02 ^a	123.25 ± 0.21 ^a

The results of micronutrients and vitamin contents are shown in Table 2.4.3. The result of Beta carotenoids content is slightly higher in extruded composite flour ($87.30 \pm 1.30 \mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) compared to non-extruded composite flour ($77.87 \pm 3.12 \mu\text{g}/100 \text{g}$). The total phenol content was slightly higher in extruded flour ($1.31 \pm 0.07 \text{ mg}/100 \text{ g}$) compared to non-extruded flour ($1.18 \pm 0.12 \text{ mg}/100\text{g}$). In terms of minerals, extruded composite flour contains slightly higher Cu ($4.51 \pm 0.14 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) and Fe ($198.51 \pm 1.81 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) than non-extruded flour (Cu: $4.31 \pm 0.31 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$, Fe: $165.99 \pm 0.01 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$). Zn levels are also marginally higher in the extruded flour ($42.59 \pm 0.82 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) compared to the non-extruded flour ($41.42 \pm 0.38 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$). The Mn content is slightly higher in extruded composite flour ($27.29 \pm 0.19 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) than in non-extruded flour ($25.68 \pm 0.23 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$). The Ca content is notably higher in extruded composite flour ($302.27 \pm 4.12 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) compared to non-extruded flour ($254.64 \pm 3.05 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$), while the Mg content is relatively similar, with the non-extruded flour ($13.06 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) slightly surpassing the extruded flour ($11.88 \pm 0.77 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$). K content is slightly higher in extruded composite flour (0.36%) compared to non-extruded flour (0.33%). Lastly, Na levels are slightly higher in the non-extruded flour ($125.34 \pm 1.25 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) compared to the extruded flour ($123.25 \pm 0.21 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$).

Shelf-life studies

The shelf studies of both extruded and non-extruded composite flour have been explained in details in D5.13.

Sensory analysis

The sensory analysis of composite flour was conducted under 5 point hedonic scale. Products were also exhibited and feedback collected (Figure 2.4.4). The details procedure is described in D5.13.

Figure 2.4.4. Some secondary School student’s taste extruded composite (left) flour during 8-8 agricultural shows and exhibition

2.4.4.2 Relevant production

Suleiman, R.A., Mwanri, A and Nchimbi-Msolla, S. (2024). Effect of Storage Conditions and Packaging Materials on Physico-chemical, sensory and microbial properties and shelf-life of extruded and non-extruded nutritious composite flour. The 9th Science, Technology and Innovation for Sustainable Development Conference to be held in Julius Nyerere International Convention Centre (JNICC) Dar es salaam Tanzania 2nd -04th December 2024.

2.4.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
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Mvomero	Two composite flours	20 farmers/food processors and 1 SMEs
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2.4.6 Summary of the impacts

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Mvomero	Composite flour	<p>New product with improved nutritional contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two composite flour (extruded and non-extruded) both enriched with higher levels of iron (+%), zinc (+%), and protein (+%). <p>Number of farmers and SMEs using the developed product</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More 40% of food processors involved in the training and production of composite flour produce flour - 100% of SMEs involved in production have successfully adopted the process and are now selling the flour.

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.4.7 Conclusions

In general, these sub-tasks have successfully identified suitable local materials and produced composite flour with improved nutritional and sensory qualities, including enhanced iron and zinc content compared to locally produced composite flour. The promising results from this work have already led to the commercial production of the composite flour by the SMEs involved in the production process. This product is expected to significantly improve the nutritional status not only of the Mvomero Food Hub but also of Morogoro and Tanzania as a whole. The next step is to submit both types of composite flour (extruded and non-extruded) to the Tanzania Bureau of Standards (TBS) for certification.

2.5 Orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, and bio-fortified beans flour

2.5.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Many flours available in Uganda are low in nutritional value and do not address the nutritional problems of under-nutrition, micro-nutrient deficiency and obesity, which are widely spread in these countries (as reported in D 2.5). Biofortified crops are specially bred to supply micronutrients of public health concern. Orange fleshed sweet potatoes are good sources of beta-carotene, a precursor for vitamin A. Biofortified beans, on the other hand are good sources of iron, zinc as well as protein. Production of these two biofortified crops has been widely promoted in Uganda. Dietary intake of these biofortified crops has however remained limited, partly because they are not available in diverse forms. Likewise, grain amaranth production has been widely promoted. Grain amaranth is relatively rich in proteins compared to staple cereals. It is also a good source of calcium, iron, zinc and unsaturated fatty acids (Muyonga et al., 2008). Technological research was undertaken to optimise formulations containing grain amaranth, biofortified beans and orange-fleshed sweet potatoes.

The objectives of the research on orange fleshed, biofortified beans and amaranth composite flour were to: i) Produce and pilot nutrient dense flours that have

potential to address nutritional gaps; ii) Determine the nutritional and physico-chemical properties of the flours produced.

2.5.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Technical components and infrastructure necessary to build the prototype, including equipment, inputs and raw materials, personnel, costs, ...

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Availability of appropriate processing equipment and facilities	M
2	Processing skills development for SME staff	M
3	Availability of quality raw materials in sufficient volumes	M
4	Connection to electricity and water supply	1
5	Products certification	M
6	Access to suitable packaging materials and equipment	1
7	Storage facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	1
8	Transportation and logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
9	Waste Management Systems: Facilities for handling and disposing of by-products or waste materials in an eco-friendly manner.	2
10	Safety and Compliance Infrastructure: Fire safety systems, first aid kits, and emergency exits for worker safety.	1

* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low

2.5.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

A total of four products were produced. Two of these were instant (extruded) and two non-instant (raw). For each of the two categories, one of the formulations consisted 3 ingredients (orange fleshed sweet potatoes, biofortified beans and grain amaranth) and one constituted 4 ingredients (orange fleshed sweet potatoes, biofortified beans and grain amaranth).

The new food raw materials used in this project included the following:

Grain amaranth: *Amaranthus hypodriacus* L., cream type, obtained from Mukono, Uganda in 2022-2024.

Orange fleshed sweet potatoes: Naspot 12 obtained from in Kamuli, Uganda in 2022-2024

Biofortified beans: NAROBAN 2, obtained from the National Crop Research Institute, Wakiso, Uganda in 2022-2024.

Maize flour was used as an additional ingredient for 2 (one instant and one non-instant) of the four composite flours developed. Maize, was used instead of pumpkins, which had been proposed as an ingredient for composite flours, because it was more available, inexpensive and the other novel ingredients (orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans) provided nutrients supplied by pumpkins.

2.5.4 Summary of the outputs

2.5.4.1 Results and achievements

The composite flours developed were generally higher in proteins, dietary fibre, beta-carotenes, iron, zinc and phytochemicals than a commercial flour, widely consumed in Uganda. Extruded composite flours generally exhibited lower peak viscosities and lower phytochemicals and antioxidant capacity than raw flours with the same ingredients. Formulations with maize were generally lower in proteins, fibre, iron, zinc and phytochemicals compared to those made from orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans only. Sensory evaluation results showed that the flours developed were all generally acceptable, with score for all attributes being >5 (on a 9 point hedonic scale) for porridge made from everyone of the flours. Extruded samples generally exhibited higher water absorption capacity, higher solubility and lower swelling power than raw samples. The differences in nutrient content of the different flours is attributable to differences in composition of the raw ingredients used. Of the components used, maize flour (refined) is generally lower in nutrients and phytochemicals, phytochemicals than other ingredients used in product formulation (Chikpah et al., 2020; Kamotho, 2020; Neela & Fanta, 2019). The

differences between extruded and raw flour can be attributed to starch pregelatinisation that occurs during extrusion (Akinwale et al., 2017). The lower phytochemicals content of extruded samples on the other hand is attributable to degradation of these components during the high temperatures recorded during extrusion (Patil & Kaur, 2018). Extruded flours also contained lower protein content. This is attributable to protein denaturation and apparent partial loss of certain amino acids and nitrogenous compounds on heating that occurs during extrusion cooking (Mosibo et al., 2022; Omosebi et al., 2018). Extruded formulations had lower values of beta carotene compared to those of raw formulations. This could be attributed to thermal degradation of beta carotene due to high temperature of extrusion (Akande et al. 2017; Waramboi et al., 2013).

2.5.4.2 Relevant production

Byamukama, J. 2024. Masters thesis - Optimizing the formulation for production of composite flour from orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, biofortified beans and maize flour. Masters thesis. Makerere University.

2.5.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Orange fleshed sweet potato, biofortified beans, grain amaranth raw and instant flour	1 SME
	Orange fleshed sweet potato, biofortified beans, grain amaranth and maize raw and instant flour	1 SME

2.5.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Orange fleshed sweet potato, biofortified beans, grain amaranth raw and instant flour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhanced SME capacity in value addition ● Business opportunity for SME ● Improved access of consumers to nutrient rich products ● Increased farmer access to market for agricultural produce
	Orange fleshed sweet potato, biofortified beans, grain amaranth and maize raw and instant flour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhanced SME capacity in value addition ● Business opportunity for SME ● Improved access of consumers to nutrient rich products ● Increased farmer access to market for agricultural produce

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.5.7 Conclusions

Technological research, pilot testing and validation shows that developed nutrient enhanced flours results in gruels that are nutritious and highly acceptable. The flours can also be used as ingredients for nutrient rich food products. If widely applied, these flours can contribute to improved nutrition in Uganda and beyond, especially for feeding nutritionally vulnerable groups such as infants and children. Successful commercial implementation of the developed

flours prototypes, however, requires food processing enterprises to invest in the production and marketing of the developed flours. It also requires sustained primary production and appropriate post-harvest handling of the targeted novel raw materials. Products certification is another prerequisite for commercial exploitation of the flours and this requires action by processing businesses and food certification bodies in respective project countries.

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2.6 Moringa and teff composite flour

2.6.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Teff is a very important crop in Ethiopia and is mainly consumed in form of njera (flat bread). Many teff growers in the Laelay Machew also grow moringa, a product with many health benefits. Despite the health benefits linked to moringa, it's consumption is limited. Technological research was undertaken to investigate the technical feasibility of blending teff and moringa, to create a a product that combines sensory acceptability, high nutrients content and high levels of health promoting bioactives. Such a product would be suitable for feeding nutritionally vulnerable population groups including infants, children, the sick, the elderly and those that are health conscious. The flours would contribute to alleviating the nutritional problems of under-nutrition, micro-nutrient deficiency and obesity, which are public health problems (as reported in D2.5).

The objectives of the research on moringa and teff composite flour was to: i) Produce and pilot nutrient dense teff and moringa composite flour that has potential to address nutritional gaps; ii) Determine the nutritional and physico-chemical properties of the flours produced.

2.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
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1	Availability of appropriate processing equipment and facilities	M
2	Processing skills development for SME staff	M
3	Availability of quality raw materials in sufficient volumes	M
4	Connection to electricity and water supply	1
5	Products certification	M
6	Access to suitable packaging materials and equipment	1
7	Storage facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	1
8	Transportation and logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.6.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Teff grains and Moringa leaves were obtained from Laelay Machew/Axum-region of Ethiopia. The raw materials were cleaned, sieved, and milled for obtaining teff flour and Moringa powder for consumption. Blending teff-Moringa flour results in five blends (i.e., teff:Moringa 100:0, 90:10, 80:20, 70:30, 60:40, 50:50, and 0:100). The independent teff and moringa leaf samples were grinded to pass through 1mm diameter sieve and analyzed in the laboratory at UoM.

Milling teff and moringa powder was continued using 0.85mm and 0.50mm diameters sieves. The grains were milled using two types of sieves to give coarse and fine milled teff flour meant to serve as ingredients for various value-added products.

The teff flower and moringa leaf powder were prepared for the physical and nutritional laboratory analysis of the composite or blended flours.

2.6.4 Summary of the outputs

2.6.4.1 Results and achievements

Teff flour showed high carbohydrate and protein contents, while Moringa leaf powder showed high ash, fiber, and protein contents. Table 2.5.1.2 reports the content of minerals in the teff and moringa. Moringa flour showed a very high calcium content, significantly higher compared to Teff ones. Iron was higher in Teff compared to Moringa, while other minerals comparable among the 2 types

of flours. Generally, the preparation of teff and moringa composite flours allows to complement their nutritional quality. Results for product analysis are reported in D 5.16.

2.6.4.2 Relevant production

Gebreyohannes Girmay, Lemlem Weldegerima and Zenebe Gebreegziabher (2024). Characterization of Teff grain (*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter)-Moringa (*Moringa olifera*, Lam) leaves composite flour, and seed oil for promoting operational nutrition in Ethiopia and Sub-Saharan Africa: in preparation.

2.6.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Laelay Machew (ET)	Composite moringa and teff flour	500 farmers

2.6.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Laelay Machew (ET)	Composite moringa and teff flour	Increasing consumption of moringa leaf powder in Axum area (being considered as medicinal)

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.6.7 Conclusions

Technological research, pilot testing and validation shows that developed moringa-teff composite flour was rich in nutrients and bioactive compounds. The flour can thus be used as an ingredient for nutrient rich healthy food products. If widely applied, the flour can contribute to improved nutrition in Ethiopia and beyond, especially for feeding nutritionally vulnerable groups such as infants and children. Successful commercial implementation of the developed flour prototype, however, requires food processing enterprises to invest in the production and marketing. It also requires sustained primary production and appropriate post-harvest handling of the targeted novel raw materials. Product certification is another prerequisite for commercial exploitation of the flours and this requires action by processing businesses and food certification bodies in respective project countries.

2.7 Tree tomato powder

2.7.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Problem(s) the prototype aims to solve or the user needs intends to address, concept, specific objectives and targets (with special attention to gender issues).

Tree tomato is a seasonal crop that produces nutrient-dense edible juicy fruits however, poor postharvest management affect their quality, nutritional and market characteristics. The fruits are climacteric, and contain high amount of water which makes them susceptible to spoilage. They are also bulk, and voluminous, hence cause major logistical challenges along the value chain. Lack of continuous, limited and sporadic supply, requires alternative for shelf stable product, as it is difficult to keep sufficient supplies of fresh fruits in the houses. The fruit is rich in chlorogenic acid which is a phenolic compound that may help prevent and treat diabetes and its complications. It can improve glucose tolerance, insulin sensitivity and reduce fasting blood glucose. Application of technological innovations to improve health food system to alleviate diseases like Diabetes mellitus (DM), which continues to pose a major public health challenge in Africa resulting in burdening of the health systems is necessary. The

innovation will address the value chain challenges for prosperity, and health food system, that is able to nourish people by ensuring easy access and availability of good quality nutritious product that is able reduce the risk of diseases like high blood sugar levels, usually associated with Type 2 diabetes (World Health Organization, 2020; UNEP, 2015).

The objective is to produce high quality tree tomato powder by pulping and solar drying.

2.7.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	25 No. Solar driers (US\$ 24,225)	M
2	Fruit pulper (US\$ 620)	M
3	Batch pasteurizer(US\$ 1,163)	M
4	Fruit washing trough (US\$ 388)	M
5	Attrition mill (US\$ 388)	M

* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low

2.7.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Drying of Tree tomato fruit pulp was carried out at the University of Nairobi (UoN) using the Innovative solar drier described in D5.10 report. The fruits were sorted, washed, blanched with hot water then pulped. The pulp was spread on a polythene support base then dried. After drying it was milled into powder, packaged and characterised using the standard AOAC methods and sensory evaluation in the Department of Food Science, Nutrition and Technology laboratory, UoN. The field validation work was carried out at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Limited (KEPC) premises in Kitui Town, Kitui Food Hub. Over 40 people who included local farmers and processors were able to learn about the new tree tomato powder production technology during the validation process, but only 37 responded to the technology acceptance assessment

questionnaire that was administered. Economic analysis of the tree tomato powder production technology was also done.

2.7.4 Summary of the outputs

2.7.4.1 Results and achievements

The moisture content, water activity and pH of the tree tomato powder were $8.66 \pm 0.009\%$, 0.41 ± 0.02 and 3.86 ± 0.045 , respectively. The low moisture content and water activity imply that the product is stable with regard to microbial spoilage. This is reinforced by its acidic nature. Rehydration ratio and hygroscopicity values were 4.42 ± 0.065 and 10.74 ± 0.067 , respectively. Rehydration ratio is a measure of how much water the tree tomato powder holds after soaking and removal of surface water, it is the ratio of the wet material to the dry material. It shows the ease of rehydration. Hygroscopicity refers to the ability of the product to absorb moisture from the environment. The equilibrium moisture content varies with the temperature and relative humidity of the surrounding air. At a given temperature the higher the relative humidity of the surrounding air, the higher the equilibrium moisture content. The product can therefore reach unsafe levels of moisture content depending on the relative humidity and the exposure time. Water solubility was respectively $87.57 \pm 0.43\%$, $97.68 \pm 0.23\%$ and $99.02 \pm 0.088\%$ at 25°C , 50°C and 80°C , respectively.

The total phenols, flavonoids and antioxidant activity were 25.56 ± 0.00 , 4.18 ± 0.000 and 1672.37 ± 0.00 mg/100 g, respectively. Beta carotene and vitamin C contents were 48.77 ± 0.00 and 348.89 ± 0.00 mg/100 g, respectively.

The average sensory test scores for the tree tomato powder were ≥ 4.3 on a scale of 5 for all attributes (appearance, aroma, taste and general acceptability).

2.7.4.2 Relevant production

The development of the following draft manuscripts is ongoing:

1. Shelf-life studies of tree tomato powder stored at ambient temperature in different packaging materials
2. Effect of solar tunnel and innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer on Functional properties of tree tomato powder.

2.7.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kitui Food Hub	Solar dried tree tomato powder	37

2.7.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kitui Food Hub	Solar dried tree tomato powder	Over 97% of the respondents who participated in the validation exercise have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available At least 5 months shelf-life High nutrient content

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.7.7 Conclusions

A tree tomato powder has been developed by solar drying tree tomato pulp. The product retains most of the nutrients and antioxidants in the fresh tree tomato pulp. Its shelf-life is at least 5 months. The technology is acceptable to farmers and processors and is economically viable. Tree tomato can grow in most arable

areas of Kenya but is currently commercially grown in only a few regions. The two levels of government should develop policies that promote the cultivation and processing of tree tomato. Consumers should be made aware of the high nutritive value of not only the fresh tree tomato fruit, but also tree tomato powder.

2.8 Dried fruits, vegetables and fish

2.8.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Tunisian diet is traditionally based on the consumption of cereals (flour, bread, pasta ...), vegetables, legumes and olive oil. Lifestyle changes have led to significant changes in diet which promoted the proliferation of non-communicable diseases as well as some malnutrition problems. Introducing food products with specific nutritional attributes and available all year long would contribute to implement a healthy diet.

2.8.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Drying Equipment: Industrial dehydrators machines suitable for fruits, vegetables, and fish products. This includes adjustable temperature and humidity controls for precision drying.	M
2	Raw Materials: High-quality fresh strawberries, eggplants, tomatoes, peppers, onions, and dam fish fillets sourced from reliable suppliers.	M
3	Food Grade Salt: Adequate supply for the preparation of salted dam fish fillets and bottarga.	M
4	Packaging Materials: Airtight, food-safe packaging such as vacuum-sealed bags, jars, or pouches to preserve freshness and prevent contamination.	M
5	Processing Area: A hygienic facility with dedicated zones for washing, cutting, drying, salting, and packaging. Must comply with food safety standards.	M

6	Storage Facilities: Climate-controlled storage for raw materials and finished products to maintain quality.	1
7	Personnel: Skilled staff trained in food processing, drying techniques, and quality control procedures. Minimum personnel: -2 Food Technologists: Responsible for overseeing the drying processes, ensuring product quality, and developing new formulations. - 4 Processing Operators: Handle machinery, prepare raw materials, and manage drying and packaging operations. 1 Quality Assurance Manager: Ensures compliance with food safety standards, monitors quality control, and supervises testing.	M
8	Quality Control Equipment: Instruments for measuring moisture content, salt levels, and microbial safety in dried products.	1
9	Utilities: Reliable access to electricity, water supply, and waste management systems for continuous operations.	M
10	Regulatory Compliance Documentation: Permits, certifications, and adherence to food safety and labeling regulations.	M
11	Transportation Infrastructure: Vehicles or logistic support for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	1
12	Cost Estimation and Budgeting: Detailed financial plan covering equipment procurement, raw material costs, labor wages, and operational expenses.	M
13	Research and Development Support: Access to lab facilities for product testing, nutrient analysis, and shelf-life studies.	2
14	Marketing and Branding Tools: Initial investment in branding, labeling, and promotional materials to establish market presence.	3
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.8.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Osmotic dehydration is the phenomenon of removal of water from lower concentration of solute to higher concentration through semi permeable membrane results in the equilibrium condition in both sides of membrane. Osmotic dehydration is the phenomenon of removal of water from lower concentration of solute to higher concentration through semi permeable membrane results in the equilibrium condition in both sides of membrane. For

strawberries conditions of OD were studied (solute concentration, duration, type of system used) and optimized through a factorial design approach. In case of eggplant and food fillet preliminary tests compared effectiveness of dry and wet salting. After OD step, samples were subjected to solar drying for their better conservation and several nutritional attributes were assessed.

2.8.4 Summary of the outputs

2.8.4.1 Results and achievements

Developed products consisted of dried strawberries, dried salted eggplant slices, dried salted fish fillets (fish obtained from dam and not commonly consumed) and bottarga. Adapted approach combining osmotic dehydration and solar drying led to development of products with interesting nutritional attributes (vitamin C, potassium, high content in protein and fat). Obtained products could be helpful to tackle nutritional gaps highlighted in Jendouba Food Hub.

2.8.4.2 Relevant production

None so far.

2.8.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Jendouba (TN)	Dried strawberries, dried eggplant, dried onions, dried tomatos, dried pepper, dried salted dam fish fillets, bottarga	20 (Women of the GDA Beni Mtir)

2.8.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Jendouba (TN)	Dried vegetable and animal products (fish)	Nutritional performance: -Food safety (decreasing moisture content and bacterial proliferation) -Food security (guaranteeing availability of developed products above season of their production) -Healthy products (proximate composition)

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.8.7 Conclusions

Valorisation of local resources through the use of sustainable and green technology are more and more recommended to tackle food security issues. Tested methods in drying agricultural products showed interesting inputs in terms of energy consumption, nutritional characteristics of dried products and particularly the facility of transfer from lab scale to field.

2.9 Dried salted, smoked, fermented fish from *Barbus altianalis* / *Labeo victorianus* Nile tilapia and African catfish

2.9.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Fish is a source of high biological value proteins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamins and minerals, with the minerals mainly concentrated in the bones

(Kabahenda et al., 2011). However, fish is highly perishable due to high levels of moisture, less connective tissues, low levels of non-protein compounds among others. Smoking, salting and fermentation are traditional fish preservation techniques that extend product shelf-life. The processes used for fish smoking, salting and fermentation are key determinants of product quality.

The overall objective was to produce palatable, safe, quality and stable preserved fish products through application of drying, smoking and fermentation. The specific objectives were:

- i) To develop novel primary processed fish products for the market
- ii) To determine the nutrient content of raw materials and value-added products

Fish preservation is expected to contribute to improvement of economic gains for the processors and fish farmers. Preservation of fish is of great importance for women in the Kajjansi/Masaka Food Hub, because women represent a high proportion of fish farmers and fish vendors.

2.9.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Raw materials: Quality fresh fish handled well (Good Hygienic Practices), quality salt, quality fish offal Nearby raw material source – lake, river, fish pond, fish processing facility</i>	1
2	<i>Equipment: Well-fabricated PAH-Safe smoking kiln, Well-constructed solar tent dryer in ideal location</i>	1
3	<i>Energy: Biomass (firewood, charcoal)</i>	1
4	<i>Others: Potable water, knives, drying rack, trays, fermentation starter culture, sugar, blender, fermentation drum/jerrycan</i>	1-2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.9.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Live fish from three species, Nile tilapia, African catfish, and *Barbus sp.* were purchased from fish farmers in Kakiri, central Uganda. The fish was transported to the food processing plant at Food Biosciences and Agribusiness Research Program (FBA), National Agricultural Research laboratories, Kawanda which is one of the NARO institutes with facilities for product development.

The smoked fish with acceptable levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) was prepared according to Masette et al., (2018) using the NARO PAH-Safe Fish Smoking Kiln

The salted fish was prepared according to the method described by Masette (2013). Briefly, the split and washed fish were sliced into thinner portions (10 mm thick). The portions were salted in 1:20 ratio (that is 0.25 kg salt for 5 kg fresh fish) then put on stainless trays overnight slanted at an angle of 20° to aid drainage of excess water. The fish portions were then spread on a raised rack mesh surface at ambient temperatures (26 - 30°C). Portions of large fish were also turned regularly (every 1 hour) and dried for 2 - 3 days.

Solar drying of fish (Nile tilapia and catfish) was done in accordance with Masette (2013). However, in this case, a solar tent dryer was used. Fish was split, thoroughly washed and then sliced into thinner portions (10 mm thickness) to facilitate the drying process. The fish was drip dried in the shade for 2-3 hours to avoid case hardening. These portions were first spread on a drying rack at ambient temperatures (26 – 30°C) before being transferred to the tent for further drying. The fish pieces in the tent solar dryer were turned at regular (1 hour) intervals and dried for approximately 2 – 4 days. The temperature in the tent solar drier was between 35-40°C.

Solid fish hydrolysate feed was produced from the fish offals/gut by lacto-fermentation (using Lactic Acid Bacteria – LAB). A method similar to Arvanitoyannis and Kassaveti (2008) was used.

2.9.4 Summary of the outputs

2.9.4.1 Results and achievements

Moisture content and water activity of salted fish products was 62.8% and 0.8 respectively. Salted tilapia had acceptable total viable counts for 6 weeks of storage and only exceeded the acceptability threshold (5 log cfu/g) in the eighth week. Salted tilapia, with overall acceptability of 6.0 remained sensorially acceptable throughout the 8 week storage period. Salting was effective for shelf life extension of tilapia.

All the dried fish samples had moisture content below the UNBS/EAS acceptable level of 15% for dried fish products. Average scores for different sensory acceptability properties were in the range 4-6 on the 9 point hedonic scale. Solar dried tilapia had borderline sensory acceptability (5.4) while solar dried catfish was not liked (3.9). This shows that the dried fish was not well liked by consumers. This could be because the dried fish products were relatively new to the consumers. Microbial counts (yeast and mould count) was within acceptable limits during the eight week storage period. Overall, the solar drying technology was able to extend the shelf life of dried fish products by at least four weeks which is the recommended minimum threshold (Mustapha et al., 2014). It is envisaged that promotion and increased awareness of dried fish products from large pelagic fish will lead to greater consumption and acceptability akin to the smoked products.

The results of proximate and micronutrient composition of feed from fermented fish offal are indicated in Table 2.9.1

Table 2.9.1 Proximate and micronutrient composition of feed from fermented fish offal

Composition (% unless stated)	Feed from fermented fish offal	EAS 90 spec (compounded poultry feed)
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Moisture content	16.19±1.52	13
Total Ash	5.31±0.18	
Crude Protein	13.62±2.02	14 – 22
Crude Fibre	3.47±0.65	7.5
Crude Fat	20.79±0.24	10 (max)
ME, Kcal/Kg	2264.14±78.16	2550 - 3000
Ca	0.41±0.16	1.0 – 4.5
P	0.71±0.25	0.7 – 1.0

The developed feed met the standard specification of a compounded poultry feed in terms of crude protein and Phosphorus. Other attributes were marginally outside recommended range.

2.9.4.2 Relevant production

Tinyiro S. E., Masette M., Akullo D., Wanda F. and Aruho C. Shelf-life assessment of improved primary processed Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and African catfish (*Clarius gariepinus*) products. 3rd FAR4ViBE Scientific Conference, Arusha, Tanzania 29th – 31st October 2024.

Masette M., Akullo D., Tinyiro S. E. and Aruho C (2023). Development of primary products from farmed fish. FoodLAND Annual meeting, Zanzibar, January 2023.

2.9.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

<i>Food Hub</i>	<i>Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)</i>	<i>n. farmers / SMEs</i>
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Dried fish (salted, smoked, fermented) from new aquaculture species (<i>Barbus altianalis</i> / <i>Labeo victorinus</i>) (dried, salted and smoked Tilapia, Catfish)	30 farmers/2 SMEs

	<i>and Barbus; fermentation for by-products, production of feed)</i>	
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2.9.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Dried fish (salted, smoked, fermented) from new aquaculture species (<i>Barbus altianalis</i> / <i>Labeo victorinus</i>) (dried, salted and smoked tilapia, catfish and <i>Barbus</i> ; fermentation for by-products, production of feed)	<p>At least 50% increase in shelf life of fish</p> <p>At least 10% reduction in fresh fish post-harvest losses</p> <p>At least 50% reduction in fish processing waste</p> <p>At least 20% increase in farmer income</p>

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.9.7 Conclusions

The develop smoked, solar dried and salted fish products had an extended shelf life. The products are nutritious and safe therefore will lead to improved health of consumers as well as increase market access for processors in local, regional and international markets. The technology used to develop is relatively inexpensive and easy to implement by local SMEs. The animal feed from lacto-fermentation of offal provides an alternative protein, energy and micronutrient source for poultry farmers while mitigating the environmental impacts of fish processing wastes disposal through adding value to them. Overall, incomes of value chain actors such as fishers, farmers and processors will be enhanced.

References

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2.10 Fish powders

2.10.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Processing of aquatic products is associated with a large amount of waste products like fish heads and bone account for about 45% of waste (Lu, 2004). A fish powder was developed from fish carcasses by milling. Nile Tilapia and African Catfish carcasses were used as base material. The overall objective was to produce safe, quality and stable preserved fish products through prolonging their shelf-life and palatability for improved economic value for the processors and fish farmers. More specifically, to develop novel milled fish products from carcasses for the market.

2.10.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Raw materials: Quality fresh fish carcasses handled well (Good Hygienic Practices) Nearby raw material source – fish processing facility	1
2	Equipment: Well fabricated stainless steel hammer mill	1
3	Energy: Electricity or Fuel	1
4	Others: Drying oven, Potable water	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.10.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Fish powder was made from Nile tilapia and African catfish carcasses by process summarised in Figure 2.10.1. By-products were separated into respective components. The belly-flaps and all fatty material were removed from carcasses and washed with potable water at room temperature. Steaming was done at 80 °C for 15 minutes to inactivate enzymes and spoilage organisms and decrease the fat content. Oven drying was done at 60°C until brittle ($\leq 10\%$ moisture content). The content was crashed using a hammer mill made from food grade materials with a sieve mesh size of 0.5 mm. The resultant powder was incorporated in maize grits in combination with other spices for the production of the extruded snack.

Figure 2.9.1. Preparation of fish powder

2.10.4 Summary of the outputs

2.10.4.1 Results and achievements

Table 2.10.1 Micronutrient composition of fish powder

Product/Nutrient composition	g/100g (%)			mg/kg (ppm)		
	Protein	P	Ca	Fe	Zn	Se
Fish powder from carcasses	12.96±1.2	9.31±1.5	17.4±2.8	71.91±3.1	45.15±1.8	1.25±0.2

The developed fish powder was rich in calcium, iron, zinc and selenium and also contained substantial protein (Table 2.10.1). The minerals content of the powder was significantly above the recommended minimum as indicated in a similar product, powdered silver cyprinid (US 780, 2012).

2.10.4.2 Relevant production

Poster presentation at FoodLAND Annual Meeting in Zanzibar, January 2023.

2.10.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Nakaseke (UG)	Fish powder from carcasses	2 SMEs and 30 farmers

2.10.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Nakaseke (UG)	Fish powder from carcasses	At least 50% reduction in fish processing waste

		Fish powder rich in micronutrients namely; Calcium, iron and zinc
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.10.7 Conclusions

The fish powder developed by milling of fish carcasses is rich in calcium, zinc and iron, This will help to enrich the diets of the consumers with these essential micronutrients. The utilization of fish carcasses will reduce the burden of disposal of processing waste by turning it into value added products. This has the double benefit of safe-guarding the environment while also enhancing incomes of processors.

References

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2.11 Quinoa-maize porridge flour

2.11.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

The quinoa-enriched porridge flour is a composite flour made of 75% quinoa and 25% maize meal. Since the quinoa grain is not grown in Kenya, the team imported it from Malawi which was cheaper than procuring it from the high-end outlets in Kenya. The maize was locally sourced. Once sourced, the grains underwent some preliminary processes such as sorting, washing and saponification before milling

and finally mixing. The saponification of the quinoa grains was done using sodium bicarbonate. The aim of the saponification process was to remove the bitter taste, caused by the saponins, to improve the palatability of the porridge flour. Both the maize meal and the quinoa were milled using a hammer mill.

2.11.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Hammer mill (US\$ 1,016)</i>	M
2	<i>Flour mixer (US\$ 5,000)</i>	M
3	<i>Flour filling, packing machine (US\$ 10,000)</i>	M
4	<i>Building (US\$ 15,750)</i>	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.11.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Brief description of the scientific-technological criteria and R&I path (development, test, and validation) for the realization of the new food raw materials / ingredients / food products.

The prototype development began with quinoa trials in the University of Nairobi Field Station from May to August 2022. Four quinoa varieties; Cherry Vanilla, Biobio, Titicaca and Brightest Brilliant Red (BBR) varieties were grown to maturity. All the four varieties did fairly well on supplemental irrigation.

The upscaling plans failed due to heavy rains experienced in the country, and this necessitated the importing of the quinoa grain from Malawi. The maize was sourced locally.

The proximate composition and mineral content analysis of the quinoa was analysed at the University of Nairobi, Department of Food Science, Nutrition and Technology Chemistry/ soil science Labs using the standard AOAC 2005 procedures and the results reported in D2.15 report. The proximate composition of the maize grain was adopted from the Kenya Food Composition Tables 2018. The formulation ratios were determined using the Nutrisurvey software 2007.

Preparation of the Quinoa grain for product development: 500g of the grain were weighed and put into a bowl containing 1.5g of Sodium bicarbonate dissolved in 1.5 litre of water. The grains were soaked for 10 minutes and later rinsed thrice using clean water. After which the grains were dried in the sun till ready for milling.

Preparation of the maize grains for product development: 125g of the maize grains was weighed and stored in plastic containers ready for blending.

Since both the maize and quinoa grains were already sorted, this step was skipped during the prototype development stage.

The quinoa and maize grains were then mixed and blended using a small-scale grinder.

The quinoa enriched porridge flour was validated in Kitui County, Kitui Central Sub-County among preschool children in Kyanika Moi Primary School. A total of seventy (70) children were involved in the validation exercise. Randomized control trial study design was used where the seventy (70) children were randomly divided into two equal groups of 35 children each. One group was fed on the quinoa enriched porridge flour while the second group was fed on the locally available porridge flour made of maize and sorghum for five (5) weeks each.

Preparation of the porridge: One and a half (1.5) kg of the composite flour was mixed with two (2) litres of water and the slurry poured into 10 litres of boiling water. The mix was then stirred unto boiling. The cooking time was 25-30 minutes using firewood. Upon cooling, the porridge the children were served

To determine the effectiveness of the quinoa-enriched porridge flour in improving the nutritional status of the preschool children, two parameters were tracked: the MUAC and the waistline. Two sets of measurements were taken at the baseline and end of the intervention, and the difference was computed.

PICTORIAL EVIDENCE OF QUINOA ENRICHED PORRIDGE FLOUR VALIDATION STUDIES

Figure 2.11.1: Saponification Process: Once the quinoa is washed with sodium bicarbonate, it produces foam as shown in this picture

Figure 2.11.2: Preparation of the quinoa enriched porridge slurry before pouring it into the boiling water

Figure 2.11.3: A sufuria containing cooked porridge

Figure 2.11.4: The study children consuming the porridge flour at Kyanika Moi Primary School

Figure 2.11.5: Enumerator taking the waistline measurement of a child at the study site

2.11.4 Summary of the outputs

2.11.4.1 Results and achievements

Product development:

A composite porridge flour consisting of 75% quinoa and 25% maize was developed. Sensory evaluation of the porridge in the laboratory revealed that it is not inferior to maize porridge in terms of appearance, taste, flavour, texture and overall acceptability. The product is very nutritious: Moisture (10%), protein (12%), fat (6%), carbohydrate (64%), Fibre (5%), ash (4%), calcium (5 mg/100 g), iron (18 mg/100 g), and zinc (5 mg/100 g).

Validation feeding trials:

The results of the feeding trials on school children in Kitui County, Kenya are shown in Table 2.11.1. There was no statistical difference in the mean difference between the two groups.

Table 2.11.1: Contribution of quinoa enriched porridge flour to the Nutritional Status of Children

		Baseline	Endline	Diff in means	p-value
MUAC	Intervention	15.53 ±1.00	19.03±15.41	3.5	0.691
	Control	15.43±0.9	18.22±13.62	2.79	
Waistline	Intervention	51.64 ±5.99	53.45±4.93	1.81	0.743
	Control	51.27±2.15	51.95±2.56	0.72	

All the values are in cm and are Mean ± Standard Deviation

Ranking of acceptance of Quinoa based porridge:

To evaluate acceptable of technology in preparation of quinoa based porridge, a seven likert scale was used for the evaluation; 7 Extremely likely, 6 quite likely, 5 slightly likely, 4 neither likely or unlikely, 3 slightly unlikely, 2 quite unlikely, 1 Extremely unlikely was used. The technology acceptance evaluation was assessed by 36 participants from Kitui County. Among the reviewers 61% (n=22) were female while 39% (n=14) were male. The adoption of the technology of preparing quinoa based porridge was scored highly for acceptance either ranking 'extremely likely' to 'quite likely' to adopt the technology (Table 2.11.2). The panellists were from the following age groups <30 yrs (6%), 30-39 yrs (28%), 40-49 yrs (25%), 50-60 years (16%) and >60 yrs were 25% of the study participants.

Table 2.11.2: Evaluation of participants acceptance of quinoa based porridge technology

Criteria	Mean	SD
Using this technology would be useful in Value addition of maize flour	6.92	0.28
Using this technology will increase the market for quinoa	6.89	0.32
Using this technology would reduce quinoa losses	6.71	0.8

Using this technology would lead to increased use of quinoa in new food products	0.28	6.92
Using this technology would increase farmers' income	0.32	6.89
Learning to operate this technology would be easy for me	0.71	6.69
I would find the quinoa-maize flour production technology easy to use	0.56	6.84
I have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available	1.45	6.51

Economic analysis

The economic feasibility of investing in milling plant to mill 578.6 tons of quinoa per annum and produce 771.4 tons of composite flour (75% quinoa and 25% maize) was analysed. Table 2.11.3 shows the investment costs.

Table 2.11.3: Investment costs

ITEM	COST (US\$)
Hammer mill	1,016
Flour mixer	5,000
Flour filling, packing machine	10,000
Building	15,750

The results of economic analysis are shown in Table 2.11.4.

Table 2.11.4: Economic analysis results

PARAMETER	VALUE
Production cost per kg powder (US\$)	4.83
Selling price per kg powder (US\$)	5.80
Benefit-Cost ratio	1.2
Return on Investment – ROI (%)	19.96

Profit margin (%)	16.54
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The results of economic analysis in Table 2.11.3 show that investment in the milling plant is economically viable. However, the selling price is very high compared to that of other less nutritious cereals because of the high purchasing price of quinoa grains.

2.11.4.2 Relevant production

- i. Thuku L., Ngala S., Kaindi D. W. M., Kogi-Makau W. (2024). Potential contribution of Kenyan-grown quinoa in improving macronutrient and micronutrient intake in children aged 2-6 years in Kenya. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development* 2024; 24(7): 26837-26857 <https://doi.org/10.18697/ajfand.132.24095>
- ii. Poster on “Novel quinoa-based products for improving the nutritional status and dietary diversity of children (2-6 years) in Kitui county”, Agricultural Show, Kitui, 27 July, 2023.
- iii. Poster on “Quality of diets consumed by children aged 2-6 years in Kitui County”. Nairobi Innovation Week, University of Nairobi, 26 - 28 April, 2024.

2.11.5 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kitui	200 children in Early education school in Kitui county	70
Kitui	Farmers, processors	37

2.11.6 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kitui Food Hub		More nutritious than pure maize flour (protein (12%), fat (6%), carbohydrate (64%), Fibre (5%), ash (4%), calcium (5 mg/100 g), iron (18 mg/100 g), and zinc (5 mg/100 g)
		Technology acceptance 6.48 on a Likert scale of 1-7 where 1 is extremely unlikely and 7 is extremely likely.
		A 19.96% Return-on-Investment

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.11.7 Conclusions

The study established that a nutrient rich porridge composite flour from quinoa and maize (quinoa at 75%), can be prepared and used to improve nutritional status of school children in Kenya.

The county government should promote the cultivation of quinoa to increase production and to lower the market price that is currently very high.

3. Overall conclusion

A variety of nutrient and nutraceutical rich novel ingredients were successfully produced. Some of these, including some of the composite flours, are suitable for direct use. I.e. they can be directly incorporated into dishes for example in

porridges or soups. Some, like fish powder, are more suitable for further processing, while others are suitable for both direct use and further processing. Regardless of the category to which the developed novel raw materials/ ingredients fall, they each have potential to contribute to dietary enrichment and food products diversification. They hence have potential to address nutritional gaps identified in D2.5 and the nutritional recommendations in D2.6. Many of the ingredients developed have been utilised in the production of processed foods (reported in D5.14), facilitating production of processed foods with superior nutritional value compared to products that are widely consumed in the FoodLAND project countries. Both the production of novel raw materials/ ingredients and their use in production of food products offer business opportunities for individuals, groups and SMEs. The developed prototypes hence create prospects for income generation and employment creation and can hence contribute to economic development. Wide adoption of the prototypes would also create demand for agricultural products, enabling farmers access markets. FoodLAND partners have undertaken technological research to develop the prototypes described in this deliverable and have disseminated the prototypes to food actors. The aforementioned economic and nutritional benefits will largely depend on the level of adoption of the developed prototypes. Continued engagement of FoodLAND partners with food actors would be helpful in promoting prototypes adoption. Partners should, if feasible, therefore continue engaging with food actors, even after the end of the FoodLAND project life.

